

Implementation of Integrated Marketing Communication at PT XYZ

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ABSTRACT

Intense competition in the economic sector forces every company and guides companies to always understand what is happening, what consumers want, and changes that exist so that every company, both developed and developing companies in this modern era, can still compete. This study aims to determine the implementation of Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC) at PT XYZ. The research design used is a case study that uses a descriptive qualitative approach by observing, analyzing data obtained from PT XYZ to conducting non-formal interviews with research subjects, then conducting descriptions or elaborations to draw conclusions. The results showed that the implementation of Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC) at PT XYZ was very effective, in the form of applying advertising, personal selling, direct marketing, sales promotion, public relations in marketing the products owned by PT XYZ. PT XYZ has implemented Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC), one of the elements implemented is Direct Marketing where salespeople make direct call offerings to offer PT XYZ products to customers.

INTRODUCTION

Intense competition in the economic sector forces every company and guides companies to always understand what is happening, what consumers want, and changes that exist so that every company, both developed and developing companies in this modern era, can still compete. In the context of corporate change, what is meant is related to what innovations are carried out by companies to be able to answer questions that consumers want, as well as changes that occur in the market. (Deden Suherman, 2017).

Marketing communications have an important role in the overall marketing mission and have a major influence on the success of the company. Marketing communication is a forum for companies to present the company and its brand and how companies can interact or establish relationships with their consumers. Implementation of marketing communications is very important in communicating the product to the target market. Many media can be used in conducting marketing communications, such as advertisements on television, radio, magazines, newspapers, posters, brochures and social media. (Utami et al., 2016)

People who are currently studying at the Kindergarten, Elementary, Middle School, High School, up to the university level and also people who are currently starting their careers, both office workers and field workers, need electronic communication devices such as smartphones, laptops and other electronic communication devices. where in the electronic communication device there is social media and many of the tools used, to access what is called the internet with the various mobile smarts they use. (Atsila et al., 2020).

The highest internet usage in 2020 was 86.5% for sending messages, 80.6% for browsing, 70.3% for social networks, 55% for video streaming, 53.8% for e-mail usage, 44.6% for downloads and the rest for online shopping, transactions, playing games, studying, video conferencing, and others. Seeing the rapid development of internet-based network access technology and the high demand for internet needs, many home internet service provider companies are competing to market their products. (Revelation, 2021).

The trend of the number of internet users in Indonesia has continued to increase in the last five years. When compared to 2018, currently the number of national internet users has jumped by 54.25%. The increase in internet users is still driven by the use of the internet which is increasingly becoming a public need, especially since the Covid-19 pandemic in 2020. Until now there are still many companies that still apply the WFH (Work from Home) work system so that the trend of working online is still going on. The government is expected to continue to support the expansion of internet coverage to all corners of the country. Because, in this digital era, the internet can really help people in accessing information, both for educational, business and entertainment purposes.

Figure 1. Internet users in Indonesia
Source : databoks.katadata.co.id

With the development of technology in today's all-digital era, of course, it is easier for everyone to communicate by building deeper, sustainable relationships. In order to communicate product values appropriately, of course, companies need HR (Human Resources) who can keep up with technological changes, and can also integrate them into a marketing communications strategy. (Diwati & Santoso, 2015).

Research conducted by Adityo Fajar (2017) entitled Implementation of Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC) at PT Tokopedia in Retaining Customers, which in the research journal explains that researchers analyzed the implementation of integrated marketing communication to increase intense competition on online buying and selling sites in Indonesia, which carries a marketplace and online mall business model. This study used descriptive qualitative method. With the results of this study indicating the implementation of Integrated Marketing Communication or Integrated marketing communications in the form of advertising, direct marketing, public relations, sponsorship, merchandising, and websites.

In an effort to transform into a digital company, PT XYZ implements a customer-oriented company business and operational strategy. The new organization is also expected to increase efficiency and effectiveness in creating a quality customer experience. Then Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC) activities are needed in marketing products owned by PT XYZ.

In today's digital era, consumers have greater access to various types of information and communication channels. Therefore, PT XYZ must understand and adopt an effective marketing strategy to reach their consumers. Research on the effectiveness of IMC can provide insight into how to integrate various communication channels, such as advertising, public relations, personal selling, sales promotion, direct marketing, events and experience, word of mouth, and interactive marketing to achieve more effective marketing goals.

The novelty in PT XYZ's Integrated Marketing Communication Implementation research continues to evolve along with changes in consumer behavior, technological developments, and marketing trends. Taking these factors into account, research can provide marketers with valuable new insights in optimizing their IMC strategy.

The IMC used in this study refers to the strategic processes that companies use to create brand communications and shape customer experiences aimed at developing lasting relationships and fulfilling predetermined goals. IMC can help PT XYZ optimize the use of their marketing budget by integrating various communication channels and delivering consistent messages. This research provides insight into ways to allocate resources efficiently and identify the most effective communication channels to achieve marketing objectives.

Advances in technology and the emergence of new media continue to change the way consumers interact with information and brands. Research on the effectiveness of IMC can help companies understand how to leverage these new technologies and media to reach consumers more effectively. Consumer behavior patterns continue to change along with technological developments and social changes. This research can help PT XYZ understand how consumers interact with various communication channels and how to influence their purchasing decisions. With this understanding, PT XYZ can adjust their marketing strategy to more effectively reach and influence consumers.

LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Priansa (2017) integrated marketing communication is a strategy, tactics and marketing activities that encourage companies to focus on their various channels to deliver a single effective message through various tools in the promotion mix. The message is able to attract the attention of the intended segment and target market. A number of integrated marketing communication activities synergistically, namely direct marketing, public relations, sales promotion, and personal selling to open up market opportunities through fostering good relations with stakeholders (Kurnia, 2022).

According to Nuraini, et al (2021) the IMC strategy implemented by a company does not only focus on offline marketing but also focuses on online marketing, resulting in a combination of offline and online. Therefore, the digital marketing side that is implemented also looks quite strong which in the end is the IMC strategy implemented by the Company in maintaining consumer loyalty. Hanafi and Wahab (2016) put forward forms of integrated marketing communication including Advertising, Public Relations, Personal

Selling, Sales Promotion, Direct Marketing, Events and Experience, Word of mouth, and Interactive Marketing.

Theodora, Nadia (2021) said that elements in integrated marketing communications consisting of advertising, public relations, events and experiences, personal selling, sales promotion, direct and interactive marketing, and WOM Marketing have an influence on the formation and development of brand equity. The same thing was conveyed by Mamosey, et al (2022) that Integrated Marketing Communication (advertising, public relations, sales promotion, personal selling, direct marketing, online marketing) simultaneously/simultaneously has a significant effect on consumer purchase intentions.

Integrated marketing communication activities require support from various company divisions, both the marketing division, research and development division, and other divisions. Integrated marketing communications is emerging as a tool that guides marketing practitioners in developing and implementing more consistent and effective marketing communications. Integrated marketing communications are capable of creating a brand image, as well as driving sales, and expanding the company's target market (Pahlevi & Nurcahyo, 2022).

The variety of product offering information that is presented in an integrated manner (Integrated Marketing Communication) will provide stimulation for consumers from various sides, making it easier for consumers to make purchasing decisions. someone in making purchasing decisions based on information received by consumers, namely through information media. With information received in an integrated manner, consumers can understand the advertised product. The better the consumer's attitude towards product information (IMC application) received, the stronger the purchase decision (Diwati & Santoso, 2015).

Integrated Marketing Communication is part of marketing communication, an important role in the implementation process. In rebranding activities, the Company can use elements of Advertising above the line (ATL) and below the line (BTL). Above the line (ATL), namely advertising broadcasts on television and radio and below the line (BTL) includes branding outlets, landmarks, pamphlets, brochures, billboards and banners (Annisarizki & Utamy, 2020).

Figure 2. Conceptual Framework Integrated Marketing Communication

METHODOLOGY

The research design used in this study is to use a case study research approach. This research will discuss the case of implementing integrated marketing communication or also known as integrated marketing communication at PT XYZ. The object of this research is Integrated Marketing Communication or an integrated marketing communication system that is applied in marketing products at PT XYZ located in Semarang.

The sources used by researchers in collecting data are primary data and secondary data. Primary data in this study were obtained from the author's observations for 3 months at PT XYZ as well as non-formal interviews with the Assistant Manager of the Customer Care Division and PT XYZ sales marketing. While the secondary data in this study are books, journals about integrated marketing communication or integrated marketing communications in the form of advertising, direct marketing, public relations, sponsorship, merchandising, and websites at PT XYZ. In this research, the writer will describe the implementation of integrated marketing communication at PT XYZ.

RESULTS

PT XYZ is a large business company engaged in the digital field that provides many superior products that are definitely needed by the Indonesian people at this time. Talking about Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC) directly intersects with elements of the promotion mix. Promotion is one way for PT XYZ to increase company revenue. Promotions carried out aim to attract potential customers and retain old customers to keep using digital products. Almost all promotions have been carried out by PT XYZ which in general, such as advertising through private radio, newspapers and television. Promotion is carried out in accordance with the agreed cooperation scheme, namely promotion carried out by the marketing sales team openly (non-partnership / direct selling cooperation scheme) by distributing brochures, banners, billboards and open tables in strategic locations. PT XYZ implements personal selling promotions carried out by the marketing sales team to visit potential customers door to door. Personal selling is not just selling, but can be a solution selling and consultative selling for customers.

According to observations for 3 months and not forgetting non-formal interviews with Assistant Managers in the Customer Care section and sales marketing, elements or dimensions of Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC) or Integrated marketing communications used at PT XYZ, include:

Advertising

Advertising is a non-personal communication that is done through the media. PT XYZ believes that the initial stage in conducting marketing communications to consumers is through advertising. The main advertising media applied is through broadcasts on television and radio. The advertisement is a long term Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC) which aims to communicate and persuade customers about PT XYZ products. Apart from that, in marketing PT XYZ products, several similar media were also applied, namely marketing communications through Brochures and Flyers, namely in the form of leaflets containing PT XYZ products. In using this marketing communication, PT XYZ uses Sales Personnel or sales individuals to disseminate it to customers. Usually the salespeople will include their names in the brochure in case the customer wants to use internet services for existing products so that the customer can confirm quickly with the salesperson and brochures and flyers will be processed quickly and distributed on the side of the road.

Sales Promotion

In informing and persuading potential customers, PT XYZ tries to stimulate customers by making sales promotions that can attract customers to use PT XYZ products. There are several sales promotions given to customers, including giving discounts to customers on special days, such as Kartini's Day, Valentine's Day, Eid al-Fitr and New Year's. This sales promotion is carried out to stimulate customers to immediately decide to make a purchase on the same day. In addition to sales promotions in the form of price discounts, PT XYZ also carries out special actions or a kind of giving gifts or souvenirs for consumers who use PT XYZ's product services who are loyal and who have been using the product for a long time. It is hoped that this provision will provide a good response from consumers who are satisfied with the services provided by PT XYZ. This sales promotion is carried out to maintain the loyalty of customers or consumers.

Public Relation

In maintaining good relations with customers, PT XYZ always pays special attention to retain customers to continue using PT XYZ products. Public Relations that is implemented in marketing PT XYZ products is through programs held by PT XYZ, one of which is the PT XYZ sharing program. In this program it is held by taking a healthy walk together while distributing gifts to the surrounding community. "Continue to do good even though it is tiring, because the fatigue will disappear but the rewards will continue to flow." This program also indirectly provides good education to the general public, especially the people of Indonesia, which teaches that business is basically intended to seek profit, but keep in mind that the benefits you get will not be

worth anything if only we will enjoy without thinking about other people around us and vice versa.

Personal Selling

Personal selling is included in personal communication that tries to inform customers about products and persuade interested customers to want to buy PT XYZ products. Personal selling is used to increase company revenue. Personal selling implemented by PT XYZ is by utilizing sales personnel. The sales persons who have been grouped into several sub-regions, will disperse every day according to the agreed-upon and determined sub-regions to find potential customers to buy PT XYZ products.

In looking for customers, salespeople don't just wait for customers to come, but they will pick up the ball or try to stimulate customers. There are several ways that salespeople usually do to stimulate customers, including opening open tables in strategic places. Next, namely door to door, on certain days the sales also do door to door from house to house to interact directly with customers to offer PT XYZ products. In addition, sales also implement marketing communications through the done line, which is closely related to Word of Mouth.

So, sales people also inform and persuade their customers by using their close friends and close people, to spread positive Word of Mouth about PT XYZ products. So indirectly this positive Word of Mouth will slowly spread to the minds of every prospective customer, and it is hoped that this will get positive feedback as well. In carrying out marketing communications, sales persons also use several media, namely brochures, flayers, banners, banners to support open table, door to door and also done line activities.

Direct Marketing

Direct marketing carried out by PT XYZ in marketing PT XYZ products is through telemarketing, which include Broadcast WA, Call Offering. Broadcast WA is usually in the form of a message that is given directly to the customer's WhatsApp number in the form of a message on the steps for uploading personal data on a paperless form in the form of a KTP photo, selfie photo with KTP, and signature, after valid or agreeing to subscribe to PT XYZ's products offered by salespeople. The messages given to new customers and old customers contain direct offers of PT XYZ products.

Next is the Call Offering which is one of the direct marketing activities carried out by PT XYZ. This activity is carried out by the sales person by calling old customers and new customers one by one until the numbers provided on the paper provided run out on the phone and later each number will be marked D (for customers who declare a deal on the offer given), M (for customers who declare Rejecting the offered offer), C (Customers whose destination number is not active when contacted), R (for customers whose number is active but when contacted does not pick up the call), O (for other problems besides the explanation of the previous symbol, such as a number that wrong destination, wrong connection number, and so on). The aim is to offer these products directly via telephone to PT XYZ's customers one by one to increase the

company's revenue. The following is a tabulation of the results of the call offering in three months.

Figure 2. Chart of Call Offering Results
 Source: Author's Processed Data, 2023

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DISCUSSION

In this study PT XYZ has implemented Integrated Marketing Communication. The elements used by the Company in Integrated Marketing Communication activities include Advertising, Public Relations, Personal Selling, Sales Promotion, and Direct Marketing. This is in accordance with the theory put forward by Priansa (2017). In addition, research conducted by Hanafi and Wahab (2016) and Theodora, Nadia (2021), Theodora, Nadia (2021) also conveyed the same thing, that Integrated Marketing Communication consists of Advertising, Public Relations, Personal Selling, Sales Promotion, and Direct Marketing.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

PT XYZ is an Indonesian digital company that offers various products and services through Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC). The company uses a variety of promotional strategies, including radio, television and radio, to reach its target audience. Sales person ensures customers are aware of product availability and receive prompt responses. In implementing Integrated Marketing Communication activities at PT XYZ, the dimensions of integrated marketing communication at PT are advertising, sales promotion, public relations, personal selling, word of mouth, and direct marketing.

PT XYZ can carry out innovations related to the implementation of dimensions in Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC) which are carried out such as innovation in organizing events, and also adding tools in the sense of a communication tool in the form of a telephone which is commonly used by sales people to carry out personal selling. It is hoped that PT XYZ will be able to start holding events which are expected to expand marketing communications. PT XYZ should also increase the available space, especially the customer care room, considering that the human resources are very adequate but the space is not very adequate to accommodate sales people.

FURTHER STUDY

The author has analyzed various integrated marketing communication channels used such as Advertising, Public Relations, Personal Selling, Sales Promotion, Direct Marketing, Events and Experience, Word of mouth, and Interactive Marketing. Evaluation of how these channels work together to deliver consistent and cohesive messages to the target audience has not been carried out by the authors. The author also hasn't conducted research on how companies allocate their marketing budget across various communication channels.

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